

DEVELOPMENT OF COMPETENCE OF ECONOMIC SPECIALISTS IN INFORMATION COMPLEXES AND TECHNOLOGIES IN THE ECONOMY (IN THE CASE OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS)

Muqimova Zulhumor Ziyataliyevna

Teacher of the "Information Technologies" department
of Fergana State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8261208>

Abstract. The article substantiates the need for the formation of information competence among students of economic specialties. The pedagogical conditions are described, the model is presented, the levels of formation of the information component in the teaching of disciplines are considered. The effectiveness of using the methodology of business games in the development of professionally oriented competencies in the process of teaching students of an economic profile is substantiated.

Keywords: methodology for the formation of competencies, motivational and cognitive components of the information competence of an economist, a model of professional competence.

INTRODUCTION

Information activity is an integral component of almost all types of professional activity, because the level of development of new information technologies requires a wide range of specialists with professional knowledge of modern software tools. In this regard, the modern information society sets the task for universities to train graduates who are able to see the problems that arise in reality and look for ways to rationally solve them using modern information technologies and programming technologies. Graduates must be proficient in computer methods for collecting, storing and processing information used in the field of their professional activities, be proficient in modern technologies for creating software for their future profession - programming skills in high-level languages, taking into account the specifics of their future profession, know the standard software for future professional activities and freely move to work with new software, independently acquire the necessary knowledge through information technologies and skillfully apply them in practice to solve functional problems.

Due to the fact that the competence approach in education is the basis of the general concept of the educational standard, one of the ways to solve this problem is the formation of information competence of students [4].

The professional activity of a future specialist cannot be successful and competitive if he does not have adequate skills to work in the modern information environment, i.e. if he does not have informational competence. Taking into account the demands of the labor market, we consider it pedagogically expedient to look for ways and conditions for increasing the efficiency of the formation of information competence of students of economic specialties, since It is in the economic sectors that information technologies become a priority. The integration of the means of forming the information competence of students into the system of professional training is an integral unity of the content, structural and methodological components of the educational process of the university and contributes to the formation of information competence.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Features of the training of future economists in the field of information technology are reflected in the studies of B.A. Bekzatova, N.V. Makarova, A.G. Stepanova, N.V. Filimonova, S.A. Chevereva, O.V. Yudina and others. A significant number of works are devoted to improving the training of students of economic specialties by various forms and means of education (A.V. Bereberdin, E.Yu. Gaidarenko, L.P. Grishchenko, M.L. Gruzdeva, A.V. Gofenberg, A. A. Evseeva, A. Yu. Orshansky, Z. A. Kolmakova, T. D. Morozovskaya, T. V. Plekhanova, E. M. Shevchenko, etc.). In their research, the authors formulate the goals of education, due to the social order, justify the selection of content, select effective and adequate methods, organizational forms and means of education.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the analysis of educational standards in economic specialties, the following most common professional competencies of students in economics can be distinguished: the ability to justify and make decisions in situations characterized by high dynamism and uncertainty; the ability to use normative and managerial, legal documentation and reference material in their professional activities; awareness of the development of the industry in which the company operates; state of research, engineering, technology, competition, dynamics of demand for products; familiarization with the work experience of specialists of a similar profile in other organizations and industries; the ability to manage resources, predict and plan the work of the enterprise, possession of ways to improve management efficiency; ability to use modern information technology, means of communication and communications; the ability to apply specialized software to solve financial, economic and legal problems [3].

Analysis of the accumulated scientific and pedagogical knowledge about information competence, concepts and hypotheses about the possibility of its formation, made it possible to systematize the signs and features of the types of information and economic activity. The most important, in our opinion, is the determination of the theoretical foundations, trends, pedagogical conditions and means of forming students' information competence.

As components of information competence, one can single out: motivational, as an internal conviction in the need to acquire new knowledge in the field of capabilities and application of information technologies and programming; cognitive as knowledge of methods for obtaining and generalizing economic information; activity, as the possession of modern technologies for creating software for their future profession; personal, as the ability to evaluate one's activities, the possession of reflection skills. The degree of students' motivational readiness for the development of personal information qualities, for the use of information technologies and programming is increased by seeing the applied aspects of the knowledge and skills acquired in the learning process through functional tasks. The cognitive level increases with a direct study of the possibilities of using computer technologies and programming for processing economic information, its correct assessment. The ways of forming the activity component in students are the development of methods for the practical application of information technologies for solving functional problems, the ability to work effectively with computer technology. In the process of creating software, debugging programs, formulating conclusions about the correct operation of software, and evaluating the information received, a personal component of information competence is formed [1].

The components of information competence are formed when teaching programming through functional tasks based on the identification of various functions of future professional

activity. The functional task should reflect the goals, the content of education, the system of professional requirements and characteristics of the future specialist; it reduces the gap between the artificiality of educational tasks and real production activities [4].

The process of forming the information competence of a student is optimized subject to the following complex of pedagogical conditions: organizational and activity, providing the possibility of using the means of forming the information competence of students; design and methodological, ensuring the readiness of the teacher to use technical and methodological means of forming information competence; psychological and pedagogical (motivational) aimed at forming students' positive motivation for self-education and self-improvement in the field of information technology [4].

Considering all of the above, it is possible to draw up a model of professional competence. It will include cognitive, functional, behavioral and ethical competencies. Functional competencies determine the ability of a person to demonstrate their work skills in practice. Behavioral competencies determine the stable characteristics of the individual associated with the performance of work. Ethical competencies include professional values, the ability to make decisions based on them in work (game) situations. As we noted earlier, the main sign that qualifies a professional is his readiness for real work, to demonstrate in practice those knowledge and skills, the possession of which is designated by the concept of professionalism. An educational institution needs to constantly update the list of competencies of a specialist graduate of an educational institution, coordinating it with customers at enterprises and developing it most carefully for each new vocational training curriculum. The range of knowledge acquired by a student in the learning process is so wide that it is difficult to put it all into practice right away. An undoubted role in modern education is played by e-learning courses with multimedia and interactive learning capabilities. They activate and individualize the process of formation of students' professional competencies, but in this article we would like to focus on another form of education.

One of the effective means of forming professional competencies in the process of teaching economics students are business games, as they contribute to solving the problem of developing professionally oriented competencies in the process of action. In our opinion, the game format is a simplified model of reality, because simulation allows you to practice almost any activity. The practice of solving non-standard problems motivates players to gain additional knowledge. Therefore, we can talk about the game as a tool that forms the motive for learning, and it is the professional competencies that the teacher should take into account when developing a "scenario" for playing the game. Business games can be classified as didactic, simulation, interactive, research, operational, business, role-playing and others. development of logical thinking and assessment by the student of his own competence in the topics covered; formation of sustainable interests in the profession. The game forms the ability to justify and make decisions in situations that are characterized by high dynamism and uncertainty, allows you to get an idea of commercial and financial transactions, models the activities of a manager, etc.

We have developed a number of recommendations that will help develop a scenario for an educational game that forms the professional competencies of students of economic specialties.

1. Students must know the list of professional competencies (according to the state educational standard).

2. The subject of the game is the subject of activity of the participants in the game, which in a specific form replaces the subject of real professional activity.

3. The roles and functions of the players should adequately reflect the "job description" of that fragment of professional activity that is modeled in the game.

4. The rules of the game should reflect the characteristics of real processes and phenomena taking place in the prototypes of the simulated reality. At the same time, the rules of the game should reflect the fact that both the models created in the game and the game itself are a simplification of reality.

5. The assessment system should provide, on the one hand, quality control of decisions made from the standpoint of the norms and requirements of professional activity, and on the other hand, an assessment of the student's competence.

An analysis of the use of gaming technologies in the application of a competency-based approach in vocational education led to the conclusion that they make it possible to increase students' interest in training sessions, allow them to learn more information based on examples of specific activities modeled in the game. . During the game, students learn to make responsible decisions in difficult situations, which will help them better navigate their professional activities (they play the active role of the head of the department, director of the company, specialist consultant, department employee or the passive role of an observer who performs control - accounting function and analyzes the results of the game). When games are played systematically and in various disciplines, it is possible to offer students (having previously explained the technology of building games) to independently simulate a game situation on a difficultly perceived topic, formulate the goal, objectives, rules of the game.

CONCLUSION

Thus, properly selected business games are an effective and indispensable tool for the formation and development of professional competencies in the process of teaching students of economic specialties, because contribute to a better and deeper assimilation of information, form a stable interest in the economic sphere of public life and the chosen specialty.

References:

1. Zeer E.F. Psychology of personality-oriented professional education. - Yekaterinburg: Ed. Ural. state prof.-ped. un-ta, 2020. - 258 p.
2. Ilyazova M.D. On the structure of the competence of a future specialist // Integration of Science and Higher Education. - 2018. - No. 1. - S. 67-72.
3. Raven J. Competence in modern society: identification, development and implementation / Per. from English. - M.: "Cogito-Center", 2022. - 396 p.
4. Sokolova I.V., Ivanchenko D.A. Training and professional activities of teachers and teachers of informatics: competence-based approach: monograph. - M.: Publishing House of the RSSU, 2010. - 212 p.

